

IGBO APPRENTICESHIP MODEL AND ENTREPRENEURIAL DEVELOPMENT OF REGISTERED SME OPERATORS IN ANAMBRA STATE

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Abstract: *The Igbo Apprenticeship Model (IAM) has long been recognized as a vital mechanism for entrepreneurial skill development and SME sustainability in southeaster Nigeria. This study examines the influence of IAM on sustainable skill specialization among registered SME operators in Anambra State. The specific objectives include: (i) identify the degree to which mentorship program sustains skill specialization among SME operators in Anambra State, and (ii) determine the extent to which cluster training model enhances skill specialization among SME operators in Anambra State. A survey research design was adopted, with data collected from 250 respondents using a structured questionnaire. Analysis was conducted using Pearson correlation via SPSS version 25. Findings revealed significant positive mentorship programs sustains skill specialization ($r = 0.662, p < 0.05$) and between cluster training models sustains skill specialization ($r = 0.699, p < 0.05$). The study concludes that mentorship and cluster training significantly enhance entrepreneurial skills and SME sustainability. It recommends the formalization and strengthening of apprenticeship programs to maximize skill acquisition and economic impact.*

Keywords: Igbo Apprenticeship Model, Mentorship Programs, Cluster Training Model, Sustainable Skill Specialization, Small and Medium Enterprises (SME)

Introduction

The Igbo apprenticeship system is a culturally embedded framework for vocational training and enterprise formation that is widely practiced among the Igbo people of South-Eastern Nigeria. Commonly referred to as *Igba-Boi/Igba-Boy*, *Imu Oru* (learning a craft), or *Imu Ahia* (learning a trade), the system is based on a contractual understanding between an established entrepreneur (the *Oga* or *Master*) and a trainee (the *Nwa-Boi* or apprentice). Through prolonged mentorship rather than formal classroom instruction, apprentices acquire practical skills, business knowledge, and entrepreneurial values. By integrating cultural norms with economic objectives, the system produces self-reliant individuals capable of establishing and managing independent enterprises after training. In this regard, the Igbo apprenticeship model functions as an informal business school that develops

human capital for small and medium enterprises (SME) and supports sustainable livelihoods across South-Eastern Nigeria (Anekwe and Osita, 2025). Historically, the development of the Igbo apprenticeship system is closely linked to the adaptive economic strategies of Igbo communities in response to major social and economic disruptions, particularly the Nigeria–Biafra Civil War and the subsequent post-war reconstruction of the 1970s and 1980s. During this period, apprenticeship became a key mechanism for wealth creation, reintegration of displaced youth, and the preservation of entrepreneurial traditions. Empirical studies demonstrate that the system continues to sustain active market networks and entrepreneurial activity, especially in prominent commercial centres such as Onitsha, Nnewi, and Awka in Anambra State (Edeh, Edeh, Oben, Okechukwu, Owere and Ule, 2025). The apprenticeship process is structured around three principal actors: (a) the *mentor*, the *Oga or the Master*, who provides hands-on training, tacit knowledge, and often access to business networks and start-up capital; (b) the *apprentice*, the Nwa Boi/ Nwa Boyi, the Odibo who offers labour and loyalty in exchange for skills and future economic independence; and (c) *family and community stakeholders*, who facilitate agreements and ensure social accountability within the apprenticeship relationship. This tripartite arrangement positions the Igbo apprenticeship system as a socially embedded learning mechanism that combines cultural obligations with economic aspirations, thereby promoting resilience and self-reliance (Familoni, 2024). The apprentice is expected to learn the business or the trade for the agreed number of years. Then, on mastering the business or the trade, the apprentice can start-up his own business and becomes a Master or an Oga (Ifeanyi, Onwuchekwa and Dimgba 2020. Ifeanyi, Onwuchekwa and Dimgba 2020 identifies several dimensions of the traditional Igbo apprenticeship system that contribute to entrepreneurship development. One key dimension is the mentorship model, which involves close and sustained interaction between mentor and apprentice, enabling the transmission of technical expertise, business ethics, and entrepreneurial behaviour. Research indicates that mentorship within the Igbo apprenticeship context strengthens operational discipline, ethical business practices, and networking capacity, all of which are essential for SME sustainability. Another important dimension is the system’s alignment with informal market clustering. Although cluster training is often discussed in relation to formal industrial districts, in the Igbo context apprenticeship activities are naturally concentrated within specialized market hubs such as automobile parts, construction trades, fashion and designing (tailoring) and agribusiness. These clusters promote peer learning, resource sharing, and cumulative skill development, while also encouraging cooperative relationships among SME operators (Mohamade and Ewuim, 2023). Together, mentorship and informal clustering significantly enhance skill specialization among SME operators in Anambra State. Mentorship socializes apprentices into core aspects of enterprise management, including customer relations, financial control, and strategic decision-making competencies that empirical studies have shown to be strongly associated with business formation and survival. Simultaneously, market clustering facilitates tacit knowledge transfer and specialization as apprentices observe best practices, identify niche opportunities, and integrate into shared supply chains that characterize highly

productive commercial ecosystems in South-Eastern Nigeria (Odeh, Onwo, Ogbuka, Agbo and Odibo, 20025). Beyond individual skill acquisition, scholars observe that the Igbo apprenticeship system contributes to broader entrepreneurial outcomes such as youth employment generation, expansion of market networks, and the long-term sustainability of registered SMEs. These outcomes are consistent with human capital theory and indigenous entrepreneurship perspectives, which emphasize culturally grounded training systems as effective drivers of microeconomic growth in environments where formal institutional support is limited (Oleka, 2025).

In contemporary practice, however, the traditional foundations of the Igbo Apprenticeship Model are experiencing notable pressure. Rapid economic transformations, urbanization, globalization, weakening communal bonds, and inadequate institutional support have collectively reshaped the effectiveness of mentorship and cluster-based training structures. Many apprenticeship arrangements now prioritize short-term labor contributions over well-structured skill development, while mentorship practices have become irregular, largely undocumented, and less oriented toward in-depth skill specialization. Furthermore, the gradual decline of organized business clusters and the limited incorporation of modern entrepreneurial practices have constrained opportunities for peer learning, innovation diffusion, and meaningful specialization among SME operators. These developments raise important concerns regarding the extent to which existing mentorship initiatives and cluster-based training mechanisms within the Igbo Apprenticeship Model continue to sustain skill specialization among SMEs in Anambra State. Diminishing mentorship quality and weak cluster structures may result in superficial skill acquisition, increased business imitation rather than specialization, reduced SME competitiveness, and limited long-term sustainability. If left unaddressed, these challenges risk weakening the IAM's historic role as a catalyst for entrepreneurship development, employment creation, and regional economic advancement.

Thus, to solve the problem identified above, the study specifically seeks to;

- ❖ Examine the degree to which mentorship program sustains skill specialization among SME operators in Anambra State.
- ❖ Determine the extent to which cluster training model enhances skill specialization among SME operators in Anambra State.

Research Questions

These questions were raised for the study:

1. To what degree does mentorship program sustain skill specialization among SME operators in Anambra State?
2. To what extent does cluster training model enhance skill specialization among SME operators in Anambra State?

Review of Related Literature

Igbo Apprenticeship Model

The Igbo Apprenticeship Model (IAM), commonly referred to as *Igba Boi/Boyi* or *Igba Odibo*, is an indigenous entrepreneurial training system that has played a pivotal role in enterprise formation and skills transmission among the Igbos of Nigeria. Conceptually, the model is anchored in informal mentorship, experiential learning, and culturally embedded norms of trust, reciprocity, and collective advancement. Rather than relying on formal curricula or certification, the system emphasizes immersion in real business environments, where apprentices acquire technical, managerial, and social competencies through observation, participation, and progressive responsibility (Ebereonwu, 2021; Umemezia & Ojukwu, 2023). Uchenna, Helen, and Anthony (2024) posit that apprenticeship-based learning significantly enhances entrepreneurial competence and business survival among SME operators in Enugu State, largely due to sustained mentor–apprentice interactions and access to start-up support. Similarly, Bala and Nyaga (2024) report that Igbo apprenticeship practices exert a positive and significant effect on business start-up among traders in Plateau State, underscoring the model’s transferability beyond its cultural homeland. Further study like Ladipo International Spare Parts Market in Mushin, Lagos State (2024) indicates that the model remains effective within diverse and competitive urban markets, where apprenticeship-trained entrepreneurs demonstrate resilience, adaptive capacity, and strong market networks (Olowu & Bello, 2024).

From a theoretical standpoint, scholars argue that the philosophical foundation of the Igbo Apprenticeship Model aligns with the principle of *Igwebuiké*, which emphasizes collective strength and shared prosperity (Adeola, 2020). This cultural orientation fosters cooperation, trust, and intergenerational knowledge transfer, positioning the model as a distinctive form of indigenous entrepreneurial education. Abba and Ugochukwu (2023) further observed that the clustering of apprentices within specific trades enhances sustainable skill specialization and contributes to regional economic development in Southeastern Nigeria.

Despite these strengths, critical scholarship highlights structural limitations within the model. The absence of standardized training frameworks and formal contractual safeguards may result in uneven skill acquisition and expose apprentices to exploitation (Umemezia & Ojukwu, 2023). Additionally, the traditional focus of the system may inadequately address emerging entrepreneurial demands such as digital literacy, formal governance, and innovation-driven growth. Nonetheless, the Igbo Apprenticeship Model remains a resilient and adaptive institution. Its demonstrated capacity to integrate mentorship, cultural values, and enterprise creation supports calls for its contextual refinement and strategic integration into contemporary SME development and entrepreneurial education policies.

The Igbo apprenticeship system is increasingly being reimagined to align with contemporary economic realities through a hybrid framework that integrates traditional practices with formal institutional structures. Recent reforms emphasize the introduction of a structured, competency-based curriculum incorporating digital literacy, accounting software, and modern customer relationship management alongside indigenous trading skills (Nnoniyelu, 2020). Verbal agreements are gradually being replaced

with documented and legally enforceable contracts to protect both masters and apprentices, addressing long-standing concerns about exploitation and unfair settlement outcomes (Eze, 2023). The system is also expanding beyond conventional trading activities into technology-driven and knowledge-intensive sectors, supported by cluster-based cooperation and access to broader entrepreneurial networks (Onyeizugbe and Orogbu, 2022). Furthermore, the settlement phase is being strengthened through formal financing options, mentorship networks, and entrepreneurial coaching rather than sole dependence on the master's resources. Cultural reforms promoting inclusivity, ethical conduct, and trust restoration further enhance the system's sustainability and relevance in a modern, competitive economy.

Mentorship Program

Mentorship is a central pillar of the Igbo Apprenticeship Model (IAM), serving as the primary mechanism through which entrepreneurial knowledge, technical skills, and ethical business practices are transmitted from experienced masters to apprentices. This long-term, relationship-based engagement enables apprentices to learn through observation, guided practice, and progressive responsibility, ensuring the acquisition of both practical competencies such as inventory management, sourcing, and negotiation and relational skills, including customer service and informal governance (Sullivan, 2000; Yani & Zaakiyyah, 2024). By combining technical training with socialization into cultural and ethical business norms, mentorship equips apprentices to manage enterprises independently and sustainably. A critical feature of IAM mentorship is structured skill acquisition, which provides systematic guidance in financial discipline, operational efficiency, and strategic decision-making. Mentors also emphasize character development and trust, evaluating apprentices for honesty, reliability, and resilience before entrusting them with sensitive business responsibilities. This ensures that apprentices are competent and trustworthy, mitigating risks and fostering long-term enterprise sustainability (Nate, Grecu, Stavytskyy, & Kharlamova, 2022).

The "Settlement" (Igba-Boi) phase represents the culmination of mentorship, where masters provide apprentices with capital, goods, or access to clients, facilitating independent entrepreneurship. Additionally, the cycle of generational mentorship sustains the system, as settled apprentices return to train new entrants, creating a self-perpetuating environment of skill transfer and entrepreneurial development. Despite these strengths, variations in mentor expertise, commitment, and adherence to traditional norms can affect outcomes, occasionally limiting skill acquisition and innovation potential (Bisk, 2002; St-Jean & Audet, 2012). Nonetheless, mentorship within IAM remains a highly effective mechanism for fostering entrepreneurial development, enhancing skill specialization, and promoting economic activity, reflecting the enduring value of culturally embedded, community-oriented apprenticeship systems (Utama, Prabowo, & Mohd, 2025; Elliott, Mavriplis, & Anis, 2020).

Cluster Training Model

The cluster training model is a vital dimension of the Igbo Apprenticeship Model (IAM), emphasizing group-based learning and skill development within concentrated marketplaces or industrial clusters.

Apprentices are trained collectively under one or multiple master entrepreneurs, gaining hands-on experience, observing diverse operational strategies, and sharing knowledge in real-time (Otsuka & Sonobe, 2018). Its core components include peer-to-peer learning, which fosters the exchange of practical insights and collaborative knowledge creation; collaborative problem-solving, which develops adaptive decision-making and equips apprentices to handle real-world business challenges; and social interaction, which strengthens ethical business practices, teamwork, networking, and understanding of market dynamics (Dzhandzhugazova et al., 2018). By integrating structured learning, collaboration, and social engagement, cluster training ensures that apprentices acquire technical expertise, practical entrepreneurial skills, and interpersonal competencies, thereby reinforcing sustainable skill specialization and preparing them for independent enterprise management, SME growth, and broader regional economic development.

Empirical studies show that cluster training enhances sustainable skill specialization and prepares apprentices for business independence (Adekunle & Okuwhere, 2025). Apprentices acquire technical expertise and practical knowledge of customer relations, resource management, and market dynamics, improving enterprise start-up success and operational resilience (Jegade, 2020). Clustered apprenticeship also contributes to regional economic growth, producing skilled entrepreneurs capable of sustaining and expanding trade networks (Mustapha, Mustapha, & Busra, 2021). However, the effectiveness of cluster training depends on cluster size, resource accessibility, and quality of mentor supervision, which can limit skill acquisition if poorly managed. Integrating modern entrepreneurial strategies, including digital skills, formal business management techniques, and innovation-driven practices, can enhance the benefits of cluster-based training for SMEs (Adekunle & Okuwhere, 2025).

Entrepreneurial Development

Entrepreneurial development refers to the systematic enhancement of knowledge, skills, and competencies required to identify opportunities, mobilize resources, manage risks, and establish or grow businesses successfully. Within the Igbo Apprenticeship Model (IAM), entrepreneurial development is largely achieved through mentorship and cluster-based learning, which combines practical experience with culturally embedded values such as trust, reciprocity, and collective responsibility (Egbetade, Onyeizugbe, & Orizu, 2024). Studies indicate that apprenticeship-trained entrepreneurs acquire both trade-specific and managerial skills that enhance business start-up success, operational efficiency, and resilience in competitive markets (Akinroluyo & Oluwaniyi, 2021).

Sustainable skill specialization involves acquiring, retaining, and effectively applying trade-specific competencies over time, allowing entrepreneurs to maintain business continuity and adapt to market dynamics. Apprentices develop such specialization through repeated practice under mentor supervision and immersion in clustered commercial environments, which provide practical insights into resource management, problem-solving, and customer engagement (Onyeizugbe, Aghara, Olohi, & Chidiogo, 2018). Demobi, Onyeizugbe, and Akpunonu (2011) further argue that skill retention and refinement directly contribute to enhanced enterprise performance and operational sustainability.

While evidence affirms the IAM's effectiveness in promoting entrepreneurial development and sustainable skill specialization, structural gaps remain. Variations in mentor expertise, lack of standardized training frameworks, limited integration of modern business practices, and inadequate exposure to digital technologies may constrain the model's capacity to produce highly adaptive and innovative entrepreneurs (Chiekezie, Nzewi, & Akinroluyo, 2021). Nonetheless, combining traditional apprenticeship methods with contemporary entrepreneurial strategies offers a viable approach to enhancing SME growth, competitiveness, and long-term sustainability.

Theoretical Framework

This study adopted Human Capital Theory (HCT), as proposed by Schultz (1961) and Becker (1964), as its preferred theoretical framework. HCT posits that individuals' skills, knowledge, and competencies constitute valuable assets that enhance productivity, performance, and economic outcomes. In the context of the Igbo Apprenticeship Model (IAM), skills acquired through mentorship programs and cluster training represent deliberate investments in human capital, which directly influence entrepreneurial competence and sustainable skill specialization. The theory is relevant because it explains how apprentices' learning and skill acquisition under the IAM translate into measurable business outcomes, including enterprise start-up, operational efficiency, and resilience. Framing the study within HCT allows for a systematic understanding of the relationship between indigenous apprenticeship practices and entrepreneurial development, providing insights for integrating traditional systems with modern SME development strategies.

Empirical Reviews

Nnonyelu (2020) investigated the declining relevance of the Igbo apprenticeship system among youths in South East Nigeria, with the objective of identifying factors undermining its contemporary appeal. The study adopted an exploratory qualitative design based on desk research, reviewing ethnographic and historical records and complemented by observational insights from informal workplaces and trading sites. Findings indicated that the apprenticeship system is challenged by poor adaptation to modern labour market demands, reduced youth interest, and limited skill modernization, posing risks to employment generation, wealth creation, and poverty reduction. The study concluded that sustaining the system requires a hybrid model that blends traditional apprenticeship structures with modern, systematic skill development. However, the study's reliance on secondary sources and lack of empirical measurement limit the generalizability of its conclusions.

Utama, Prabowo and Mohd (2025) examined the integration of business course mentorship programs and investment opportunities to enhance entrepreneurial outcomes. The study aimed to determine how structured mentorship and access to capital influence entrepreneurial skills and business success. Using a survey design with 320 undergraduate students enrolled in entrepreneurship programs, data were collected via structured questionnaires and analyzed using regression and correlation techniques. Results indicated that mentorship programs combined with investment opportunities significantly improved entrepreneurial competencies and business readiness. While comprehensive in linking

mentorship to practical outcomes, the study was limited by its focus on students, which may not generalize to informal or SME-based apprenticeships.

Adekunle and Okuwhere (2025) investigated the role of the Igbo Apprenticeship Model in promoting innovation among SMEs through cluster-based training. Employing a mixed-method approach with 200 SME operators in Southeast Nigeria, the study combined surveys and interviews to examine the effect of clustering on skill specialization and business performance. Findings revealed that clustering enhances innovation, knowledge sharing, and resilience among entrepreneurs. Methodologically strong, the study could have benefited from longitudinal tracking to assess sustained business outcomes over time.

Ogbogu and Emeka (2025) examined apprenticeship in Igbo land and its effect on venture success in Anambra State. The study aimed to determine the effects of seed capital, mentorship, and apprenticeship training on venture success. Anchored on skill acquisition theory, a survey research design was adopted. From a population of 4,212 respondents, a sample size of 809 was determined using the Borg and Gall formula. Data were collected using structured questionnaires whose reliability was confirmed through test–retest and Spearman rank correlation ($R_s = 0.79394$). Data analysis involved descriptive statistics and ANOVA. Findings revealed that seed capital, mentorship, and apprenticeship training significantly influenced venture success. The study concluded that the Igbo apprenticeship system positively affects entrepreneurial outcomes. Methodologically, the large sample size strengthens external validity; however, the heavy reliance on self-reported data limits objectivity, and the cross-sectional design restricts causal inference.

Antai, Okpong, Jufri, Imiefoh, Collins and Aidonojie (2024) conducted a legal examination of the contractual status of the “Nwa Boyi” within the Igbo Apprenticeship Model in South-East Nigeria. The study aimed to assess how the traditional apprenticeship system aligns with formal legal frameworks. Using doctrinal legal analysis and sociocultural theory, the study relied on secondary legal sources, customary practices, and theoretical interpretation rather than empirical sampling. Findings revealed significant gaps between customary agreements and statutory contract law, exposing apprentices to legal vulnerabilities. The study concluded that legal reforms are necessary to formalize contractual protections. While conceptually strong, the absence of primary empirical data and sample-based analysis limits its practical generalizability and empirical robustness.

Helen, Ihezue and Marilyn (2024) examined the challenges and prospects of the Igbo apprenticeship system in the modern world. A descriptive survey design was adopted, focusing on Enugu State. From a population of 276 apprentices across major markets, a sample size of 163 respondents was selected. Data were analyzed using mean, standard deviation, chi-square, and simple regression analysis. Findings showed significant challenges confronting the system, alongside strong prospects for its sustainability. The study concluded that policy intervention is required to address master–apprentice disputes. Methodologically, the use of inferential statistics strengthens analytical rigor; however, the geographically restricted sample limits national representativeness.

Eze (2023) assessed the Igbo apprenticeship system in Nigeria with the objective of evaluating its effectiveness and sustainability. The study employed a descriptive and analytical approach, drawing on secondary data and qualitative interpretations of existing practices. Findings indicated that while the system remains effective in skill transmission and entrepreneurship development, it faces modernization and regulatory challenges. The study concluded that reform and institutional support are necessary. The major limitation lies in the absence of primary data and a defined sample size, which weakens empirical depth and replicability.

Nnonyelu, Nnabuife, Onyeizugbe, Anazodo and Onyima (2023) examined Igbo apprenticeship (Igba Boyi) as an exemplar of indigenous African entrepreneurship. Drawing extensively from a 2021 field study of Onitsha Market, the research adopted a qualitative and contextual analytical approach. Findings revealed that apprenticeship graduates exhibit superior resilience, managerial competence, and entrepreneurial dexterity. The study concluded that the model is scalable for African development. Although rich in contextual insight, the study lacks methodological transparency regarding sample size and data analysis procedures, which limits methodological rigor.

Onyeizugbe and Orogbu (2022) evaluated cluster cooperatives as a model for poverty reduction in Delta State. Using a survey design, data were collected from six cluster groups comprising 125 members. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were applied. Findings showed that cluster cooperatives facilitated access to microcredit and reduced poverty, though training and supervision were inadequate. The study concluded that strengthening cluster alliances would enhance poverty reduction outcomes. While the methodology is adequate, the small sample size and focus on a single program constrain broader applicability.

Nnonyelu (2020) interrogated the practice and declining appeal of Igbo apprenticeship among youths in South-East Nigeria. The study adopted an exploratory qualitative design, relying on desk research, ethnographic and historical records, and observation across informal workplaces. Findings indicated that modernization pressures, weak regulation, and declining incentives have demarketed apprenticeship. The study concluded by proposing a hybrid apprenticeship model. Methodologically, the qualitative depth is a strength; however, the absence of empirical sampling limits generalizability and policy precision.

Oyewunmi, Oyewunmi and Moses (2020) analyzed the historical transitions of the Igbo apprenticeship model. Using a historical and qualitative analytical approach, the study traced Igbo enterprise development from pre-colonial times through post-civil war recovery. Findings emphasized the centrality of Igba-Boi in entrepreneurial regeneration. The study concluded that sustainability requires institutional adaptation. While theoretically rich, the lack of empirical measurement and sample-based analysis restricts its classification as a fully empirical study.

Kanu (2019) examined Igwebuikconomics as a framework for wealth creation through Igbo apprenticeship. The study employed a philosophical and conceptual approach, emphasizing communality and shared prosperity. Findings suggested that apprenticeship fosters inclusive wealth

creation. However, the absence of empirical data, methodology, and sample size significantly limits its empirical relevance.

Iwara, Amaechi and Netshandama (2019) investigated the Igba-Boi apprenticeship approach as a driver of entrepreneurial success. Using a qualitative survey design, purposive sampling was employed to conduct interviews and focus group discussions with experienced entrepreneurs. Data were analyzed using thematic analysis with Atlas.ti. Findings identified three stages of apprenticeship: identification, learning, and settlement. The study concluded that legal involvement is necessary to address settlement disputes. Methodologically, the qualitative rigor is strong, but the lack of sample size disclosure limits transparency and replicability.

Methodology

This study adopted a quantitative research design to examine the relationship between the Igbo Apprenticeship Model (IAM) and entrepreneurial development, specifically focusing on sustainable skill specialization among registered SME operators in Anambra State. The target population comprised all registered SME operators within selected trade clusters across the state. A purposive sampling technique was employed to select 250 SME operators who had undergone apprenticeship training under the IAM, ensuring that participants possessed relevant experiential knowledge. Primary data were collected using a structured questionnaire designed on a five-point Likert scale, measuring the dimensions of the IAM mentorship programs and cluster training models and the dependent variable, sustainable skill specialization. The instrument was pre-tested for validity and reliability, achieving a Cronbach's alpha of 0.87, indicating high internal consistency. Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics, including mean scores, standard deviations, and Pearson's correlation analysis to examine the relationships between the independent and dependent variables. Hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 significance level, allowing for determination of statistically significant associations between mentorship programs, cluster training models, and sustainable skill specialization. The methodology ensured a rigorous, empirical assessment of the effectiveness of the IAM in fostering entrepreneurial skills and SME sustainability, providing insights relevant to both policy and practice.

Results

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of SME Operators

Variables		Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	160	64
	Female	90	36
	Total	250	100
Educational Qualification	Non-formal Education	20	8
	Primary	40	16
	Secondary	90	36

	Tertiary	100	40
	Total	250	100
Business Type	Retail	80	32
	Manufacturing	50	20
	Services	70	28
	Agro-processing	30	12
	Others	20	8
	Total	250	100
Year of Business Operation	Less than a year	25	10
	1–5 years	120	48
	6–10 years	75	30
	11 years and above	30	12
	Total	250	100
Years Under Apprenticeship	Less than 1 year	40	16
	1-3 years	100	40
	4-6 years	70	28
	7 years and above	40	16
	Total	250	100

The demographic profile of the 250 SME operators show that male operators (64%) dominated, while females accounted for 36%, reflecting the male prevalence in SMEs and the Igbo Apprenticeship system. In terms of education, most respondents had tertiary (40%) or secondary (36%) education, suggesting that formal education complements skills acquired through apprenticeship. Regarding business type, retail (32%) and services (28%) were most common, with manufacturing, agro-processing, and other businesses making up the remainder, indicating a diverse range of SME operations. Years of business operation showed that nearly half (48%) had 1–5 years of experience, while years under apprenticeship revealed that 40% trained for 1–3 years and 28% for 4–6 years. Overall, respondents were moderately experienced, educated, and well-exposed to apprenticeship training.

Test of Hypotheses

H₀₁: Mentorship programs does not significantly sustain skill specialization of registered SME operators in Anambra State.

Table 2: Model Summary of Pearson Correlation

		Mentorship Programs	Sustainable Skill Specialization
Mentorship Programs	Pearson Correlation	1	.662
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.001
	N	250	250
Sustainable Skill Specialization	Pearson Correlation	.662	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	250	250

. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Spss Output, 2026

The null hypothesis (H0₁) stated that there is no significant degree to which mentorship programs sustains skill specialization of registered SME operators in Anambra State. The Pearson correlation coefficient from Table 2 is $r = 0.662$, with a p-value of 0.001, indicating a strong positive relationship between mentorship programs and sustainable skill specialization. The p-value is below the 0.05 significance level, meaning the correlation is statistically significant. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. This finding implies that effective mentorship programs under the Igbo Apprenticeship Model significantly enhance sustainable skill specialization. Apprentices gain practical knowledge, technical competence, and strategic insight, which improve their entrepreneurial performance, enterprise resilience, and long-term sustainability in the SME sector.

Hypothesis Two

H0₂: Cluster training model does not significantly enhance skill specialization of registered SME operators in Anambra State.

Table 3: Model Summary of Pearson Correlations

		Cluster Training Model	Sustainable Skill Specialization
Cluster Training Model	Pearson Correlation	1	.699
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.010
	N	250	250

Sustainable Specialization	Skill	Pearson Correlation	.699	1
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.010	
		N	250	250

. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Spss Output, 2026

The null hypothesis (H₀₂) stated that there is no significant extent to which cluster training model enhances skill specialization of registered SME operators in Anambra State. Table 3 shows a Pearson correlation coefficient of $r = 0.699$ with a p-value of 0.010, indicating a strong positive relationship. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the correlation is statistically significant. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. This finding implies that participation in cluster training significantly enhances sustainable skill specialization. Apprentices gain practical experience, exposure to market dynamics, peer learning, and problem-solving opportunities within clusters, which improve technical competence, entrepreneurial capacity, and business resilience. The result confirms that the cluster training model under the Igbo Apprenticeship framework is a vital mechanism for skill development and SME sustainability.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study reveal a significant positive relationship between mentorship programs and sustainable skill specialization as well as between the cluster training model and sustainable skill specialization among registered SME operators in Anambra State. These results align with the findings of Ohazuruike and Elechi (2023), who observed that the Igbo Apprenticeship System, through structured governance and mentorship, plays a critical role in developing entrepreneurial competencies in southeastern Nigeria. The current study confirms that mentorship provides apprentices with practical guidance, ethical business practices, and strategic insights, enabling them to acquire specialized skills that enhance enterprise sustainability.

Similarly, the findings resonate with Abba and Ugochukwu (2023), who emphasized that the apprenticeship style, particularly through group-based learning in market clusters, fosters practical skill acquisition, peer learning, and entrepreneurial resilience. The strong positive correlation observed in this study between cluster training and skill specialization supports their conclusion that clustered apprenticeship arrangements promote exposure to market practices and resource-sharing, which are crucial for SME survival and growth.

Conclusion

This study concludes that the Igbo Apprenticeship Model, through mentorship programs and cluster training, significantly enhance sustainable skill specialization among registered SME operators in Anambra State. Mentorship provides practical guidance and ethical business practices, while cluster

training promotes peer learning, market exposure, and resource-sharing. These mechanisms collectively strengthen entrepreneurial competence, enterprise resilience, and long-term SME sustainability. The findings affirm the relevance of indigenous apprenticeship practices in fostering skill development and economic growth, highlighting their potential integration into contemporary SME development strategies.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made:

- i. Mentorship programs should be strengthened by ensuring structured guidance, regular monitoring, and systematic transfer of technical and managerial skills. Apprentices should have access to experienced mentors, and trade associations or government agencies can provide mentor training to improve quality, accountability, and effectiveness.
- ii. Cluster training models should be promoted and formalized to facilitate peer learning, resource-sharing, and exposure to market practices. Integrating modern business practices, including digital skills, financial management, and innovation strategies, into cluster training will enhance entrepreneurial competence and SME resilience.

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